

CLASSIC MUSICS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6304746>

Rafikjon Akhmedov

senior teacher of "Folk Art" department, Fergana regional branch of
Uzbekistan state institute of arts and culture

Anotatsiya: *Shunday kuy-qo'shiqlar borki, ular faqat bir-ikki emas, minglab, millionlab insonlarning shodligiga sherik, dardlariga malham bo'ladi. Bunday kuy-qo'shiqlarni mumtoz asarlar deb ataymiz. Mumtoz kuy-qo'shiqlarni har qanday san'atkorlar ham maromiga yetkazib ijro eta olmaydi. Buning uchun chinakam iste'dod sohibi bo'lish lozim. Ular ijro etgan qo'shiqlar o'zbek san'atimizning durdonasi sifatida oltin fondga saqlanyapti.*

Аннотация: *Есть песни, которые разделяют радости и печали тысяч и миллионов людей, а не одного или двух. Мы называем эти песни классикой. Классическую музыку не может исполнять ни один артист. Для этого нужно быть действительно талантливым. Исполненные ими песни хранятся в золотом фонде как шедевр узбекского искусства.*

Annotation: *There are songs that share the joys and sorrows of thousands and millions of people, and not just one or two. We call these songs classics. No artist can perform classical music. The songs they performed are stored in the golden fund as a masterpiece of Uzbek art.*

Keywords: *classical melodies, methods of performance, classical poets, teacher-student tradition*

Classical musics include maqoms, complex melodies and songs of large form, which are the rarest products of the work of skilled musicians, singers and composers. In practice, they are also called "classical melodies" or "professional melodies". This means that classical music is one of the best examples of professional folk art. The works of this genre are created by talented composers and performed by highly qualified singers and musicians. The meaning is complex and perfect. Therefore, to perform them requires a great deal of artistic experience, skill and musical literacy. Classical melodies have long been taught to young people by teachers. The classical melody consists of large-scale melodies and songs. They are diverse in content and form. It is known that our country is divided into 4 major oases in terms of dialect. These are:

1. Bukhara - Samarkand 2. Khorezm 3. Surkhandarya - Kashkadarya 4. Fergana is the Tashkent oasis. Sheva is reflected not only in language, but also in music. Music culture is a factor that strengthens the closeness and friendship between peoples. The future of a nation with a great culture is also great. The heritage of classical music of our spiritually rich people is incomparable. Classical

melodies are the spiritual nourishment of our people created by teachers, musicians and composers. is a sign. Therefore, if the artists of each epoch respect the past of their people, classical music, rely on it and continue their traditions, they will have done a worthy job for the future. If any modern creation is irrigated by the traditions of the past, it is natural that it will be a successor of the Nation. Classical melodies come in two forms. One is instrumental music and the other is singing. The composition of instrumental music includes works ranging from the simplest folk melodies to complex maqom samples. Among them are many traditional classical works, as well as maqom instruments. Classical melodies have long been performed by Uzbek folk instruments such as tanbur, dutar, gijjak, nay, chang and surnay. There are a lot of classical melodies that our people love to listen to. They are called "Hojiniy I II", "Gulizorim", "Dilxiroj", "Ey sabo", "Kocha baghi I II", "Abdurahmonbegi", "Aylagach", "Fig'on", "Sensan sevarim", "Munojot", "Tanovar", "Choli iraq", "Mirzadavlat", "Munojot", "Ufori Munojot", "SavtiMunojot", "Ilgor", "Rohat", "Rajabiy", "Sharof I II", "Ushshaqlar" There are several types of "Ferozlar", "Bayot", "Suvoralar", "Chorgohlar" and "Ushshak". Examples of such melodies are "Sodirkhan ushshoghi", "Aliqambar", "Koshchinor", "Navruz Ajam". There are many famous people among our people who created and performed classical musical melodies. Among them: Usta Olim Kamilov, Yunus Rajabiy, Tukhtasin Jalilov, Saidjon Kalonov, G 'anijon Toshmatov, Fakhriddin Sodiqov, Muhammadjon Mirzayev, Turgun Alimatov, Ahmad Odilov, Abduhoshim Ismoilov, Olmas Rasulov, Kahramon Dadaboyev and others. Classical melodies are composed of lyrical ghazals and poems by classical writers such as Jami, Navoi, Fuzuli, Babur, Mashrab, Khorezmi, Ogahi, Nodira, Muqumi, Furkat, Charkhi. The Independence Day has opened a wide way to revive the heritage of folk music and its colorful traditions. It would be useful to include in this tradition the tradition of educating students through the example of teachers. In particular, Mulla Toychi Tashmuhamedov, Domla Halim Ibodov, Hoji Abdulaziz Abdurasulov, Jurahon Sultanov, Mamurjon Uzokov, K. Otaniyozov, Orifkhon Hotamov, the founders of the Uzbek school of singing, are among their favorite artists. That is why every artist wants his classical music to be popular and to be engraved in the pages of history. To do this, they must be worthy of their profession in all respects and have a traditional character. The topic we have chosen is to recall the works of Haji Abdulaziz Abdurasulov, Komiljon Otaniyozov and Orifkhon Hotamov. It is safe to say that their unique works, songs and melodies, inherited for future generations, are already in the hearts of our beloved people, and today their musical works have become the rich musical heritage and property of the Uzbek people. They are always sung, renewed and rejuvenated by our people because they have left a rich spiritual, national musical heritage that honors love, the country and the Motherland. From this point of view, the more our young people study this rare musical heritage, the less it seems. Thus, it remains an important

task to educate our youth in the spirit of the works of folk singers and composers of Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES:

1. Karimov I.A. Uzbekistan has its own path to independence and development.-Т .: Uzbekistan, 1992.-22 p.
2. Karimov I.A. The homeland is as sacred as a shrine.-Т .: Uzbekistan, 1993.- 350 p.
3. Uzbekistan on the path of independent development.-Т .: Uzbekistan, 1994.-49 p.
4. Karimov I.A. Creativity is the basis of a prosperous life.-Т .: Uzbekistan 1995.- 46 p.
5. Karimov I.A. Turkestan is our common home. –Т .: O'zbekiston, 1995.-46 p.
6. Karimov I.A. On the way to deepening economic reforms in Uzbekistan.- Т .: Uzbekistan, 1995.- 245 p.
7. Karimov I.A. National independence of Uzbekistan, economy, politics, ideology.-Т .: Uzbekistan, 1995-348 p.
8. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". Harmoniously developed generation is the basis of development of Uzbekistan.-Т .: Sharq, 19983 В 20-29.
9. Mahmud Ahmedov. Hoji Abdulaziz Abdurasulov. Tashkent. Teacher Publishing House. 1974 y.
10. Olimjon Gafurova and others. Abdulaziz Hofiz. Samarkand 1996
11. S.Begmatov. Orifxon Hotamov. Tashkent. "New Age Generation". 2000 y.
12. Matyokubov O. Introduction to the basics of professional music in the oral tradition. Tashkent Teacher Publishing House. 1983 y.